

Analysis of Employee Capability at Dinas Pekerjaan Umum dan Tata Ruang (PUPR) of the Mentawai Islands Regency

Rifki Eriawan¹⁾, Deltri Apriyeni²⁾, Hendra Yuharmain H³⁾, Reymond Chandra⁴⁾, Robertius⁵⁾
^{1,2,3,4,5}(Master of Management ·STIE KBP Padang)
 Corresponding Author: Deltri Apriyeni

Abstract:- This study was conducted to have the goal to be achieved to determine capabilities in the Performance of PUPR (PUPR) in the Mentawai Islands District. This is motivated by the still need to improve employee skills, the low motivation of employees to work, some employees who are not on time to work, there still many inappropriate work results, the availability of inadequate job data, and employee performance that is still not stable in the Public Works Department and Spatial Planning of the Mentawai Islands District. Multiple linear regression is an analytical tool with quantitative methods used in research. The research respondents were 71 people. The method for sampling method used total sampling. The research hypothesis was tested with the IBM Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24.0 system. Based on scientific test results, especially partially competence, work motivation, and work discipline had a positive and significant effect on employee performance, and simultaneously competence, work motivation, and work discipline jointly had a positive and significant effect on the performance of the PUPR Office employees. Mentawai Islands District.

Keywords:- Competence, Work Motivation, Work Discipline, Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District as an organization that always strives to develop the quality of its human resources has the task of handling the work of the state government in the field of PUPR assigned to the regions and additional tasks assigned to the regions.

For the PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District, the issue of employee performance is an important factor because employee performance is very influential on the success of regional government administration, especially regional autonomy. The selection of PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District as the focus of research is based on the decline and instability of institutional performance achievements in 2019, 2020, and 2021, related to the previous explanation, that humans are the most decisive resource of many other resources. This is because human resources can work effectively and efficiently among other resources that are dependent on human resources who use them. This is because human resources can work effectively and efficiently among other resources that are dependent on human resources who use them.

The following is a table of performance achievements from programs/activities carried out at the Mentawai Islands District PUPR Office for the period 2019 to 2021, namely:

Table 1. Program/Activity Performance Report

No.	Programs / Activities	Target (%)	Realization (%)		
			2019	2020	2021
1.	Office Administration Service Program	100	68	70	67
2.	Apparatus Facilities and Infrastructure Improvement Program.	100	63	65	68
3.	Apparatus resource capacity program	100	69	65	63
4.	Improvement Program for Performance and Financial Performance Reporting System Development.	100	70	63	60
5.	Regional Financial Management Improvement and Development Program.	100	65	70	70
6.	Village Financial Management Guidance and Facilitation Program.	100	65	65	70
Average		100	66,3	66,6	66,3

Source: Secondary Data, PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District, 2022.

As seen from table 1, The Program/Activity Performance Report above shows that the average program/activity realization is experiencing instability and is still below the average of the agency's performance target. This can be seen from several realizations of the programs/activities of the PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District, namely: The office administration service program in 2021 was 67 percent, a decrease from the previous two years; The program for improving the facilities and infrastructure of the apparatus in 2021 is 68 percent, an increase from the previous two years; The apparatus resource capacity program in 2021 was 63 percent, a decrease from the previous two years; The program to increase the development of the performance and financial achievement reporting system in 2021 by 60 percent decreased from the previous two years; The program for improving and developing regional financial management in 2021 by 70 percent does not experience an increase or decrease, and the program for fostering and facilitating village financial management by 70 percent in 2021 has increased from the previous year.

From these data it can be concluded that the PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District has not been maximized and there are still several problems within the agency, all of that cannot be separated from the human resources contained in it, both from the system or its implementation, so that the targets and realization of work program evaluations from year to year have decreased. Performance requires a process in doing it, the most influential are members of the organization/ institution/ company, however, the main problems that are often found are competence, work motivation, and organizational performance is low due to the impact of undisciplined employees.

This can be seen from the phenomena that occur in the field, the initial assessment of the performance of employees at the PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District can be seen in the table below:

Table 2. Employee Performance Assessment Data

No.	Phenomenon	Amount (person)	Average (%)
1.	Employees who still need to improve their skills	35	50,7
2.	The low motivation of employees to work	39	56,5
3.	There are still employees who often come late	30	43,5
4.	There's still a lot of work that doesn't match	32	46,3
5.	Inadequate availability of job data.	37	53,6
Average		35	50,1

Source: Author's initial observations, 2022.

Based on the tabulation in table 2, it can be explained that the phenomenon that occurs is that in general, employees still need to improve their skills with an average value of 50.7 percent. the statement about the low motivation of employees to work with an average value of 56.5 percent. Then there are still employees who often arrive late with an average value of 43.5 percent, there are still many work results that are not followed per under an average of 46.3 percent, and the availability of inadequate employment data with an average of 53.6 percent. Based on the findings obtained, there are performance problems in human resources at the research location in the PUPR Mentawai Islands District. For this reason, this research is very important to do because good employee performance will accelerate the achievement of institutional goals. Based on secondary data and observations at the research location, it is suspected that the factors that are of concern to PUPR of the Mentawai Islands Regency are; employee competence, work motivation, and employee work discipline.

Currently, the need to meet the demands of education has increased in the scope of the agency or organization. Therefore, there are many demands, one of which is the totality of achieving the educational goals of a nation. Aspects related to performance support are reliable human resources (HR) to achieve organizational goals if it is not based on good performance, the organization's goals cannot be achieved

(Hayati, 2010). According to Simamora (2012), Performance is the fulfillment of certain job requirements, which can be directly reflected in the quantity and quality of the work.

Competence is a basic quality of the workforce and is a determining factor for a person's success or failure at work or in certain situations Mc. Lelland in (Moehariono, 2012).

Work motivation plays a role in influencing performance apart from competence. Sunyoto (2013) regarding this matter is; a person will have strength if he has motivation from within himself to make ends meet. Then Simamora (2012), explains further about work discipline, as a way to give punishment to subordinates who do not comply with the rules. Someone who has discipline will easily control himself so that team cohesiveness and seriousness in work will create an advanced and developing organization.

From the phenomena that have been described previously, this study is very useful for the institution concerned. Therefore, the study in this study will discuss the influence of competency, work motivation, and work discipline both partially and simultaneously on employee performance at PUPR of the Mentawai Islands Regency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Employee Performance*

The performance itself is the value of a series of work behaviors that contribute, both positively and negatively, to the completion of the work (Wibowo, 2017). Furthermore, Fadel (2009) divides performance indicators, namely: 1. Understanding of main tasks and functions, 2. Innovation, 3. Work speed, 4. Work accuracy, 5. Cooperation.

➤ *Competence*

According to Mc. Lelland in (Moehariono, 2012), Competence is a basic quality of the workforce and is a determining factor for a person's success or failure in work or certain situations. The competency indicators according to Ruky (2006), namely: 1. Consistent, 2. Attitude and Value System, 3. Information and Scope of Work, 4. Ability to Complete Technical Tasks and Ability to Complete Managerial Tasks dan 5. Directing and guiding.

➤ *Work Motivation*

The indicators of work motivation according to Achievement of organizational goals require optimal efforts

and are largely determined by a person's ability to do business to fulfill his life needs Robbins (2016), indicators of work motivation include; 1. Physiological needs, 2. Need for security, 3. Social needs, 4. Appreciation needs, 5. Self-actualization needs.

➤ *Work Discipline*

According to Siswanto (2013), work discipline is an attitude of respect, respect, and obeying the applicable written and unwritten rules, and can enforce these regulations and will not avoid sanctions if he violates his duties and obligations. The indicators of work discipline according to Siswanto (2013), namely: 1. Attendance and punctuality, 2. Accuracy and calculation, 3. Rules and responsibilities, 4. Obedience and agility, 5. An atmosphere of harmony and mutual respect.

➤ *Framework*

Explanation of the theoretical basis and presentation of the research problem formulation that has been described can describe the conceptual framework used in the research so that the basic concepts studied in this study are clearer, namely:

Fig 1. Research Conceptual Framework

➤ *Hypothesis*

Based on the conceptual framework above, in this study the following hypotheses can be formulated:

- H1: Competence Affects the Performance of PUPR Office Employees of Mentawai Islands District
- H2: Work Motivation Affects the Performance of Employees of PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District
- H3: Work Discipline Affects the Performance of Employees of PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District
- H4: Competence, Work Motivation, and Work Discipline Influence on the Performance of PUPR Officers of the Mentawai Islands District

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research is quantitative research. The analysis technique used is Total Sampling. The context of this research variable is competence, work motivation, work discipline, and employee performance. Data is processed using IBM SPSS Version 24.0. In line with the type of research, the data used is quantitative. In line with the type of research, the data used is quantitative. Quantitative data is data from the

results of the questionnaire given to the research sample. This research is supported by primary data and secondary data to describe the research problem. There are two primary data sources in this study, namely: obtained directly from direct observation and recording of the primary real state of resources and administration and directly from the respondents with a tool in the form of a questionnaire about research variables that become a problem in this research of government employees who are employees of the Office of PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District. The use of secondary data in this study was obtained indirectly or through intermediary media according to research needs to describe related phenomena.

Data analysis was used to see whether there was a relationship between competence, work motivation, and work discipline on the performance of PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District. The analysis carried out is descriptive analysis, validity analysis, reliability analysis, classical assumption test, namely normality test, heteroscedasticity test, and multicollinearity test, then hypothesis testing is carried out with multiple linear regression tests.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

I. Result

A. Classic Assumption test (Normality test)

The purpose of doing the normality test is to test whether in the regression model the confounding variables or the residuals are normally distributed so that the data becomes feasible. This is because the t-test and F-test assume that the residual values follow a normal distribution for the conditions

for the regression test (Hair, 2006). In this study, the normality test used was; the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Decisions are made based on this normality test to look at the Asymp probability. Sig (2-tailed). If the probability Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) > $\alpha=0.05$, then the residual data is normally distributed. In the following, the results of the normality test using the One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test are presented. Based on calculations via a computer using the IBM SPSS for Windows Version 24.0 program, it can be explained through the following table :

Table 3. Normality Test Results

No.	Variable	Asymp. Sig	Limit Value	Information
1	Standardized Residual	0,200	0,05	Normal

Source: Primary Data, IBM SPSS Ver. 24.0, the year 2022.

In table 3 above it can be explained that the standardized residual variable in the processed data has a significance value of $0.200 > 0.05$. Thus it can be concluded that the confounding variables (residual) in each variable used in this study are normally distributed.

observation that occurs in the data, for that a heteroscedasticity test is performed. It is expected that what happens to the data is homoscedasticity so that the data becomes accurate. This study used the Glejser test by regressing the independent variables to non-standard residual values. Note that if the significant value is greater than 0.05, it means that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity in the research data. The following results of processed data are ;

B. Heteroscedasticity Test

A good regression model is that there is no difference in variance from the residual one observation to another

Table 4. Heteroscedasticity Test

No.	Variable	Residual Absolute (RES_ABS)	
		Significant	Conclusion
1.	Competence	0,294	Free of Heteroscedasticity
2.	Work motivation	0,238	Free of Heteroscedasticity
3.	Work Discipline	0,696	Free of Heteroscedasticity

Source: Primary Data, IBM SPSS Ver. 24.0, the year 2022.

Based on data from table 4, it can be explained that the significant value of the variables processed has a significant value greater than 0.05, meaning that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity (free of heteroscedasticity) in the regression model.

influence each other in the regression model. To see the occurrence of multicollinearity in the regression model by looking at the tolerance value and variance inflation factor (VIF). With the interpretation that if the tolerance value is less than 0.10 or the VIF value is greater than 10 then multicollinearity occurs, if the tolerance value is greater than 0.10 or the VIF value is less than 10 then multicollinearity does not occur. The results of this multicollinearity test are presented in the following table :

C. Multicollinearity Test

The correct regression model should not have symptoms of multicollinearity, it is necessary to test the model. The purpose of this test is to test whether the independent variables

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test

No.	Independent variable	Tolerance	VIF	Conclusion
1.	Competence	0,707	1.415	Free of Multicollinearity
2.	Work motivation	0,707	1.415	Free of Multicollinearity
3.	Work Discipline	1,000	1.000	Free of Multicollinearity

Source: Primary Data, IBM SPSS Ver. 24.0, the year 2022.

Based on the processed data in table 5 above, it can be concluded that the independent variables, namely competence, work motivation, and work discipline, have no symptoms of multicollinearity because the two independent variables have a tolerance value greater than 0.10 and VIF is less than 10. So the data fulfills the elements regardless of the multicollinearity element.

D. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

To prove that there is a relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, a multiple linear regression test is performed. The purpose of this test is to answer the hypothesis according to the research problem.

Based on the tests performed, the following results are obtained :

Table 6. Recap of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Variable	Coef. Regression	t-count	Sig.
Constant	15,662		
Competence	0,742	8,534	0,000
Work motivation	0,299	4,401	0,000
Work Discipline	0,115	2,250	0,034
F-count = 62,662	Sig. 0,000		
R² = 0,737			

Source: Primary Data, IBM SPSS Ver. 24.0, the year 2022.

From the results of the processed data listed in table 6 above, the form of the regression equation model for the influence of the independent variables is; competency, work motivation, and work discipline on the dependent variable namely; employee performance is as follows:

$$Y = 15,662 + 0,742.X_1 + 0,299.X_2 + 0,115.X_3 + e$$

Explanation of the above equation:

$\alpha = 15,662$; the meaning of this value is; without the influence of independent variables or competence, work motivation, and work discipline, the dependent variable or performance is 15.662 percent in this study.

$b_1 = 0,742$; the meaning of this value is that there is a positive influence between the competency variable (X1) on performance (Y) based on the results of processed data. The meaning is, increasing the value of competence will improve employee performance considering the relationship that occurs is positive. Then it can be explained further that the competency regression coefficient value is 0.742 meaning that for every increase of one competency unit, employee performance increases by 74.2 percent based on the results of processed data.

$b_2 = 0,299$; from the results of processed data, there is a positive influence between the variable work motivation as an independent variable (X2) on performance as the dependent variable (Y). It can be concluded that the increase in work motivation that occurs will also increase employee performance. Shown by the value of the regression coefficient of work motivation of 0.299, meaning that for every increase of one unit of work motivation, the employee's performance increases by 29.9 percent concretely.

$b_3 = 0,115$; from the processed data it can be concluded that; there is a positive influence between the independent variables or work discipline (X3) on performance (Y). This description shows that there is an increase in work discipline will be able to improve employee performance on the object of research. The work discipline regression coefficient value of 0.115 means that for every increase of one unit of work discipline, employee performance increases by 11.5 percent according to the results of processed data.

E. T-test (partial)

Based on the results of processed data in table 6 it can be explained that :

1. Effect of Competency variable (X1) on Performance variable (Y).

The results of the analysis of the influence of the Competency variable (X1) on the Performance variable (Y) obtained the value of t count = 8.534 (df = 71-4 = 67; t table = 1.99601); (t count > t table), with a significant level of 0.000 < 0.05, as a result, the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted. The results of the analysis show that part there is a significant influence between the competency variables on the performance of PUPR employees of the Mentawai Islands District.

2. The Effect of Work Motivation (X2) on Performance (Y)

The results of the analysis of the influence of the work motivation variable (X2) on the performance variable (Y) obtained the value of t count = 4.401 (df = 71-4 = 67; t table = 1.99601); (t count > t table), with a significant level of 0.000 < 0.05, as a result, the null hypothesis (Ho) unacceptable and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) can be accepted. Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between work motivation as an independent variable on performance as the dependent variable for employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency.

3. There is an influence of the independent variable or Work Discipline (X3) on the dependent variable or Performance (Y).

Based on the results of the processed data, the analysis of the effect of the Work Discipline variable (X3) on the Performance variable (Y) obtained the value of t count = 2.250 with (df = 71-4 = 67; t table = 1.99601); (t count > t table), with a significance level of 0.034 < 0.05, thus the null hypothesis (Ho) cannot be accepted and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) can be accepted. Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that partially (t-test) there is a significant influence between the independent variable of work discipline on the dependent variable or the performance of employees of the Mentawai Islands Regency PUPR Office.

F. F test (simultaneous)

Based on the results of processed data in table 6 it can be explained that the results of the analysis of the influence of the

independent variables are; Competence (X1), Work Motivation (X2), and Work Discipline (X3) simultaneously (together) on performance (Y), obtained an F count value of 62.662 with a significant probability of $0.000 < 0.05$. With $df_1 = (k-1) = 3$, $df_2 = 71 - 4 = 67$, F table 2.74, then $F_{count} > F_{table}$ or $62.662 > 2.74$, as a result, H_0 is unacceptable and H_a is acceptable. From the results of data analysis simultaneously (together) there is a significant influence between the variables of competence, work motivation, and work discipline on the performance of the employees of PUPR of the Mentawai Islands District.

G. Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

From the results of the multiple linear regression tests that have been carried out, the coefficient of determination or R Square is 0.737, which means; a 73.7% variation of all independent variables (competence, learning motivation, and work discipline) can explain the dependent variable or employee performance. The remaining amount of 26.3 percent cannot be explained by this model but can be explained by other variables not examined in this study. From the results of data processing carried out it can be found that; the value of R^2 is away from the number 0 (zero) and close to the number 1 (one), meaning that the contribution (influence) of the independent variable or the independent variable simultaneously on the dependent or dependent variable has a strong relationship.

2. Discussion

A. The Effect of Competence on Performance

Based on the formulation of the problem and the research objectives to be achieved is to find out how much influence competence has on employee performance at the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency. From the results of processed data, the analysis of the influence of the Competency variable (X1) on the performance variable (Y) obtained a t value of 8.534 ($df = 71-4 = 67$; t table = 1.99601); meaning ($t_{count} > t_{table}$), with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, then the null hypothesis (H_0) cannot be accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) can be accepted. Thus it can be explained that part there is a significant influence between the independent variables or competence on the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency. Therefore it can be stated that competence has a significant effect on the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency. One of the determining factors for the performance of employees of the PUPR Office in the Mentawai Islands Regency is the competence of these employees.

An explanation of competence as an ability based on skills and knowledge is then supported by work attitudes and behaviors related to the specified job requirements (Sutrisno, 2011). further Mc. Lelland in (Moehersono, 2012), explains competence as a basic quality of the workforce and is a factor that also determines the success or failure of a person in doing a particular job or situation. Furthermore, Wibowo (2013), added that competency is considered one of the factors that influence performance. At work locations or in certain situations. Skills are needed in assisting an organization in

creating a work culture at a higher level. The number of skills mastered by human resources will be able to improve performance. Martin in (Priansa, 2017), states that a manager is someone who carries out competency activities according to their function referring to employee development activities.

The results of this study are in line with and also support the results of research by (Erwansyah et al., 2018), (Junaidi, 2021), and (Fadillah et al., 2017) who found that competency variables or independent variables in this study a significant effect on employee performance. It can be concluded that; it the importance of paying attention to the competence of an agency because good competence will affect the performance of an employee which in turn will affect the performance of the agency as a whole. The better the competence of employees at work, the better the performance of these employees. And the faster the realization of organizational goals.

B. The Effect of Work Motivation on Performance

Next is the second goal to be achieved in this study, namely to determine the effect of the independent variable work motivation on the dependent variable or the performance of employees of the Mentawai Islands Regency PUPR Office. Based on the results of the analysis of the effect of the work motivation variable (X2) on the performance variable (Y), the t value was 4.401 ($df = 71-4 = 67$; t table = 1.99601); ($t_{count} > t_{table}$), with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be explained that the null hypothesis (H_0) cannot be accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) can be accepted. The results of the analysis conducted show that there is a significant influence between the variables of work motivation on the performance of employees of the Department of PUPR, Mentawai Islands Regency.

Based on the results of the study it can be explained that work motivation has a significant effect on the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency. Thus it can be concluded that the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency is determined by one of the employee's works motivation.

This is reinforced by the statement (Sunyoto, 2013), which explains that motivation is a force that results from a strong desire within a person to satisfy their needs. Added ; (Hasibuan, 2016), that motivation relates to how to direct the power possessed and potential in subordinates, so that they want to work together productively to achieve and realize the goals that have been determined. Thus it can be concluded that work motivation is a process in which the need to encourage someone to carry out a series of activities that lead to the achievement of certain desired goals.

Based on the results of the previous analysis, this research is in line with and supports the findings of research results (Sekartini, 2016), (Andriyani et al., 2021), and (Paryanti & Rasmansyah, 2020), it was found that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance. Therefore it is necessary to draw the following

conclusions; work motivation of an agency is something that needs to be considered and is very important because work motivation can affect the performance of an employee which will ultimately affect the overall performance of the institution. The better and higher the employee's motivation at work, the better the employee's performance.

C. The Effect of Work Discipline on Performance

The following is the third research objective, namely; to determine the effect of the independent variable work discipline on the dependent variable or the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency. Based on the results of the data analysis conducted, it was found that the effect of the Work Discipline variable (X3) on the Performance variable (Y) obtained a t value of 2.250 ($df = 71 - 4 = 67$; $t \text{ table} = 1.99601$); so that ($t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$), with a significance level of $0.034 < 0.05$, the null hypothesis (H_0) cannot be accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) can be accepted. This condition shows that part there is a significant influence between work discipline variables on the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency.

Thus, based on the results of the acquisition of data analysis, it can be seen that work discipline has a significant effect on the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency. So it can be concluded that the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency is determined of them by work discipline.

As stated by; Hasibuan (2014), the sense of responsibility of an individual in carrying out the tasks and responsibilities given is reflected in the attitude and discipline in completing the task. It facilitates the joy of work, morale, and the achievement of the set goals of the agency. Therefore, all leaders must always try to direct their members to good work discipline to create order in the organization. Namely by providing guidance and direction to employees. In (Simamora, 2012), argues that work discipline is a procedure for correcting or punishing subordinates who violate the rules and procedures that have been regulated as a provision that must be implemented. High discipline is a form of self-control and effective implementation for an employee, evident from the seriousness of the work team within the organization.

The results of this study are appropriate and supported by research before this study was carried out, including; (Erwansyah et al., 2018), (Prasetyo & Marlina, 2019), and (Rastana et al., 2021), that work discipline a positive and partially significant effect on performance. Thus the conclusion that can be drawn from this study is that the performance of an employee is influenced by work discipline. The better the work discipline of an employee, the better the employee's performance.

D. The Influence of Competence, Work Motivation, and Work Discipline on Performance

Following is the fourth objective which is the final objective that must be achieved in this study is to determine the effect of competence, work motivation, and work

discipline or all of the independent variables on the dependent variable or the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency. Based on the results of data analysis it is known that the influence of competence (X1), work motivation (X2), and work discipline (X3) simultaneously (together) on performance (Y), obtained an F count of 62.662 with a significant probability of $0.000 < 0.05$. With $df_1 = (k-1) = 3$, $df_2 = 71 - 4 = 67$, F table 2.74, then $F_{\text{count}} > F_{\text{table}}$ or $62.662 > 2.74$, then H_0 is unacceptable and H_a is acceptable. Based on the calculations in the data analysis it appears that simultaneously (together) there is a significant influence between the variables of competence, work motivation, and work discipline on the performance of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency.

The results of this study as a whole show that competence, work motivation, and work discipline have a significant effect on the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency. Therefore it can be concluded that the performance of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency is determined simultaneously by the variables of competence, work motivation, and work discipline.

Performance or performance is a picture of the level of achievement of goals, objectives, vision, and action plans to carry out the mission or organizational policies as outlined in the organization's strategic plan. The same thing was also conveyed (Wibowo, 2016), performance is the value of a series of work behaviors that contribute, both positively and negatively, to the completion of how it works.

The results of this research study are in line with and support the theories and expert opinions regarding competence, work motivation, and work discipline which simultaneously affect performance. The results of this study concur with and support the results of research before this study was conducted, carried out by (Suparno & Sudarwati, 2014), (Andriyani et al., 2021), and (Irfan et al., 2020). Based on theoretical studies, expert opinions, and the results of previous research as previously described, it can be stated that there is a significant influence of competence (X1), work motivation (X2), and work discipline (X3) on employee performance (Y). It can be explained that there is a positive and significant relationship and influence, with the understanding that when competence, work motivation, and work discipline improve, performance can increase. The results of the hypothesis test from this study, namely competence, work motivation, and work discipline simultaneously have a significant influence on the performance of employees of the PUPR Office of the Mentawai Islands Regency.

V. CONCLUSION

Moving on from the results of testing the hypothesis, it can be concluded in this study, namely; The independent variables tested including competence, work motivation, and work discipline had a positive and significant effect on the dependent variable or the performance of employees of the Mentawai Islands Regency PUPR Office. Based on the research findings and conclusions, the authors suggest the

following; first, all employees of the Mentawai Islands District PUPR Office so can pay attention to performance, both in terms of understanding tasks and functions, innovation, speed of completion of work, accuracy in work, and cooperation with colleagues. Second, pay attention to competence, be more consistent, pay attention to attitudes and value systems, understand information and scope of work, be able to complete technical and managerial tasks, and improve cooperation in work teams.

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